

ACTION OF SULPHUR DIOXIDE WATER ON PERMANGANATES OF BARIUM AND SILVER

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Action of normal sulphurous acid on 1% solution of barium permanganate and 0.5% solution of silver permanganate has been studied.

When normal sulphurous acid reacts with solutions of barium and silver permanganates, about 88-89% of it is oxidised to various sulphur acids (SO_4^{2-} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$). The rest is lost due to volatilisation of sulphur dioxide during the preparation and addition of normal sulphurous acid. Free sulphuric acid, metal sulphate and dithionate and manganese sulphate are the various products of reaction. A precipitate of the general composition $x\text{RO} \cdot y\text{MnO} \cdot z\text{MnO}_2$ is formed. With the increasing volumes of the sulphurous acid the amount of precipitate decreases until it vanishes completely. Finally, total manganese is accounted for as sulphate, and the metal, as sulphate and dithionate both.

Previously, the action of normal sulphurous acid on permanganates of calcium and ammonium (Lal and Singh, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 547; Lal and Mehra, *ibid.*, 1956, 33, 668) has been reported. In the present investigation the action of normal sulphurous acid on permanganates of barium and silver has been attempted.

EXPERIMENTAL

Barium Permanganate.—Barium permanganate employed in the present investigation was prepared by the method recommended by Muthmann (Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. XII, p. 333, Longmans, Green & Co., London, 1947). It was filtered through an asbestos filter and preserved in a well-stoppered bottle in dark. Its purity was tested and exactly a 1% solution, required for the present investigation, was prepared by dilution.

The intermediate stage of the reaction was studied by adding freshly prepared normal sulphurous acid to barium permanganate solution (50 c.c., 1%), dropwise in duplicate, until the purple colour of the permanganate was just discharged. Only sulphate and dithionate were detected in the filtrate. It gave no tests for barium, manganese, thiosulphate and higher thionates.

The sulphate content was estimated as barium sulphate in cold (Mitchel, "Modern Methods of Chemical Analysis", p. 136) and the dithionate by oxidising it with potassium bromate and HCl (conc.) as previously done (Lal and Singh, *loc. cit.*). The total normality of the acids, determined by alkali titration, was found to correspond with the sum of those calculated from sulphate and dithionate estimations (H_2SO_4 , 86.8% and $\text{H}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, 13.2%), thus indicating that sulphate and dithionate, both, must be present as free acids only.

The dark brown precipitate was found to consist of hydrated manganese dioxide, manganese oxide, barium oxide and barium sulphate. Manganese dioxide was estimated by the method used by Mohammed and Ahluwalia (this *Journal*, 1941, 18, 309). Barium sulphate was separated and estimated from the remaining solution. Total manganese was

removed as sulphide from the solution left over and then estimated as pyrophosphate (Gooch and Austin, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1898, 18, 339). The amount of barium present as barium oxide in the precipitate was estimated as barium sulphate from the solution after removal of the manganese sulphide. The manganese oxide content was determined from the total manganese and that corresponding to manganese dioxide. The molar ratio of BaO : MnO : MnO₂ came out to be 1 : 4 : 19.

The reaction was further studied with one-half and three-fourth of the volume of the *N*-sulphurous acid required for the intermediate stage. The amounts of unchanged MnO₄⁻ were estimated by titrating against ferrous ammonium sulphate solution. Barium being absent, the MnO₄⁻ was accounted for as HMnO₄ in the filtrates. Small amounts of dithionate also were produced in these experiments. From the results the molar ratio of BaO : MnO : MnO₂ in the precipitate appears to be 1 : 4 : 19 again.

More experiments were repeated with the increasing volumes of the *N*-sulphurous acid. Just after the intermediate stage, formation of some manganese sulphate was also noticed, and subsequently an increase in the amount of this product continued until the total amount of manganese was converted into manganese sulphate (expt. No. 6, Table I). The acidic character of the filtrate became more and more pronounced due to the formation of increasing quantities of sulphuric and dithionic acids. Formation of any thiosulphate and higher thionates was not detected in these experiments also. The intensity of the colour as well as the amount of the precipitate formed during this stage was found decreasing with the increasing volumes of the sulphurous acid. A regular decrease in the quantity of manganese dioxide with a corresponding increase in the manganese oxide content of the precipitate was observed. Finally the product became absolutely white and free from oxides of manganese and barium. It was only barium sulphate. In expt. Nos. 4 and 5, the molar ratio of BaO : MnO : MnO₂ comes out to be 1 : 7 : 21 and 1 : 23 : 27 respectively against 1 : 4 : 19 in expt. Nos. 1 to 3, Table I.

In expt. No. 6, the total amounts of manganese and barium, both, are accounted for as sulphate, the former remaining in the solution and the latter, due to its insoluble character, in the precipitate. A decrease in the sulphuric acid content in expt. No 6 further suggests that after the complete reduction of manganese dioxide to manganese oxide, the latter perhaps reacts completely with sulphuric acid according to the equation,

showing thereby that manganese dioxide acts as a negative catalyst in the reaction. The analytical values of this experiment may be expressed by the equation,

Again purified sulphur dioxide gas was passed through barium permanganate solution (50 c.c., 1%) for a long time. The precipitate consisted of barium sulphate only and the filtrate gave tests for sulphate, sulphite (from unchanged sulphurous acid), dithionate and manganese. Formation of any thiosulphate and higher thionates was not detected.

TABLE I

Products of reaction with N-H₂SO₃ + Ba(MnO₄)₂.

Total Ba added = 0.1827 g. Total Mn added = 0.1467 g.

(The values inserted being mean of the duplicate experiments).

Expt. No.	H ₂ SO ₃ added.	Ba (MnO ₄) ₂ (% decomp).	BaSO ₄ .	MnSO ₄ .	H ₂ S ₂ O ₆ .	H ₂ SO ₄ .	BaO : MnO : MnO ₂ (mol. ratio)	BaO : MnO : MnO ₂ (mol. ratio, approx).
1	5.00 c.c.	53.35	0.2960 g.	Nil	0.0198 g.	0.0682 g.	1 : 4.38 : 18.59	1 : 4 : 19
2	7.00	79.69	0.2894	"	0.0270	0.1721	1 : 4.31 : 18.81	1 : 4 : 19
3	9.85	100.00	0.2858	"	0.0383	0.2539	1 : 3.94 : 18.79	1 : 4 : 19
4	11.95	"	0.2960	0.1178 g.	0.0466	0.2589	1 : 7.28 : 20.59	1 : 7 : 21
5	14.05	"	0.3068	0.2194	0.0536	0.2733	1 : 23.24 : 27.01	1 : 23 : 27
6	16.40	"	0.3098	0.4027	0.0572	0.2479	Nil	Nil

Silver Permanganate.—A freshly prepared solution of normal sulphurous acid was added likewise to silver permanganate solution (100 c.c., 0.5%) till the colour of the permanganate was just discharged. The filtrate gave tests for silver, sulphate and dithionate only. It was distinctly acidic due to the formation of sulphuric acid. No manganese was detected in the filtrate. Silver, quantitatively estimated as AgCl, was accounted for as sulphate and dithionate, both, which were estimated respectively as in the earlier section. The analytical data are recorded in Table II. The dark brown precipitate on quantitative analysis gave values of 1 : 1 : 6 for the molar ratio of Ag₂O : MnO : MnO₂. The compound by analogy may be called silver manganous hexamanganite.

The investigation was continued with one-half and three-fourth of the normal sulphurous acid required for the intermediate stage (expt. Nos. 1 and 2, Table II). Each filtrate contained unchanged silver permanganate, silver dithionate and some sulphuric acid. In the precipitates the same compound, *i.e.* silver manganous hexamanganite, was observed throughout.

TABLE II

Products of reaction with N-H₂SO₃ + AgMnO₄ (100 c.c., 0.5%)

Total Ag added = 0.2379 g. Total Mn added = 0.12115 g.

(The values inserted being mean of the duplicate experiments).

Expt. No.	H ₂ SO ₃ added (% decomp).	AgMnO ₄	Ag ₂ SO ₄ .	MnSO ₄ .	Ag ₂ S ₂ O ₆ .	H ₂ SO ₄ .	Ag ₂ O : MnO : MnO ₂ (mol. ratio).	Ag ₂ O : MnO : MnO ₂ (mol. ratio, approx.).
1	4.20 c.c.	54.57	0.1471	Nil	0.0200 g.	0.1257 g.	1 : 1.20 : 6.45	1 : 1 : 6
2	6.30	82.67	0.2133	"	0.0397	0.1849	1 : 1.095 : 6.17	1 : 1 : 6
3	8.50	100.00	0.2581	"	0.0469	0.2641	1 : 1.25 : 6.23	1 : 1 : 6
4	10.70	"	0.2581	0.1240 g.	0.0678	0.2677	1 : 2.25 : 4.92	1 : 2 : 5
5	12.90	"	0.2589	0.2391	0.0992	0.2676	1 : 21.22 : 5.33	1 : 21 : 5
6	13.40	"	0.2583	0.3326	0.1024	0.2295	Nil	Nil

Lastly, with the increasing volumes of normal sulphurous acid (expt. Nos. 4, 5 and 6, Table II), the value of silver sulphate was found to be constant and a regular increase in the amount of silver dithionate was observed. The presence of sulphuric acid was detected in each experiment. The molar ratio of $\text{Ag}_2\text{O} : \text{MnO} : \text{MnO}_2$ comes out to be 1:2:5 and 1:21:5 respectively (expt. Nos. 4 and 5). In expt. No. 6 no precipitate was left. The total amount of silver was accounted for as sulphate and dithionate, both, and that of manganese, as sulphate only. A decrease in the sulphuric acid content, in this investigation also, supports the view represented by equation (1). The reaction in expt. 6 may be represented by the equation,

Further, purified sulphur dioxide gas was passed through silver permanganate solution (100 c.c., 0.5%) till the dark brown precipitate first formed was completely acted upon. The clear solution showed tests for sulphate, sulphite (due to unchanged sulphurous acid), dithionate, manganese and silver only. Any thiosulphate and higher thionates were not formed in this reaction also.

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